

Parenting Partner Involvement in Postpartum Parenting and Mental Health Interventions: A protocol for a scoping review

Authors

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Abstract

Objective: To map and characterize the literature on postpartum mental health and parenting interventions that report any form of parenting partner involvement, detailing how they are engaged, to what extent, and how their participation influences intervention processes or outcomes.

Introduction: Although partner-inclusive adaptations of postpartum interventions have demonstrated benefits for maternal symptoms and family functioning, existing syntheses rarely specify the nature or depth of parenting partner engagement and often exclude mother-initiated or informally shared participation of parenting partners. This scoping review seeks to clarify the full spectrum of parenting partner involvement and the role of partners in enhancing postpartum maternal well-being.

Inclusion criteria: Eligible sources will involve mothers aged ≥ 18 years who have given birth within the past five years and their parenting partners. We will include any mental health or parenting intervention delivered in the postpartum period that documents partner engagement—whether direct (e.g., joint sessions) or indirect (e.g., material shared via mothers). All settings, delivery modes, prevention or treatment levels, study designs, and outcome types are eligible; reviews and opinion pieces will be excluded, but their reference lists will be hand-searched.

Methods: Searches will be conducted in MEDLINE, Embase, PsycINFO, CINAHL Plus with Full Text, Web of Science, SocINDEX, and ProQuest Dissertations & Theses (inception–August 2025), with no language or date limits, using database-specific controlled vocabulary and keywords. Titles/abstracts will be screened independently by two or more reviewers, followed by full-text keyword searching and eligibility assessment. Data will be charted in a standardized form and summarised with descriptive statistics and thematic grouping; results will be presented in tables and narrative form in accordance with JBI and PRISMA-ScR guidance.

Keywords: co-parenting, partner support, postpartum mental health, partner engagement, scoping review

Introduction

Mental health concerns during the postpartum period, such as depression and anxiety, are common (C.-L. Dennis et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2017) and pose significant health concerns for both the mother (woman-identifying individuals who gave birth and is the primary caregiver of an infant or young child) and the newborn. Higher rates of suicide, substance misuse, and life-threatening health complications are observed in mothers with mental illness (Slomian et al., 2019). Reports of difficulties with infant bonding and harsh parenting (e.g., spanking, yelling, shaming) are well-documented among mothers with elevated depressive and anxiety symptoms (Reck et al., 2018; Seymour et al., 2015; Slomian et al., 2019). In response, various therapeutic and educational interventions for postpartum mothers were developed (Howard & Khalifeh, 2020). Partner-inclusive adaptations of these interventions emerged as the evidence demonstrating the importance of parenting partner inclusion in maternal mental health and infant development burgeoned (e.g., Hannon et al., 2022; Lever Taylor et al., 2018; Rhodes et al., 2021). Studies have demonstrated the efficacy of partner-inclusive interventions for a range of mental health and parenting-related outcomes. However, little is known about *how* parenting partners are involved in these interventions and its effects on outcomes.

Evidence of efficacy of partner-inclusive postpartum interventions are substantial. A systematic review by Noonan et al. (2021) found that eight of nine partner-inclusive interventions for postpartum depression led to significant symptom reductions. Pilkington et al. (2015) examined partner-inclusive interventions for both postpartum depression and anxiety in their systematic review, and nine of the 13 included studies reported significant reduction in symptoms. A qualitative systematic review by Alves et al. (2018) identified enhanced communication and mutual understanding among parenting couples as potential mediating factors across partner-inclusive postpartum depression interventions. For parenting-specific challenges such as breastfeeding (Abbass-Dick et al., 2019), a partner-inclusive approach was found to increase breastfeeding initiation, duration, and exclusivity. Similarly, over half of the studies included in Jeong et al.'s (2023) systematic review found significant positive effects of partner-inclusive interventions on maternal and infant health and nutrition outcomes. Lastly, a systematic review of parent education programs inclusive of fathers found that across 21 studies, overall improvements in father's engagement was reported including co-parenting and supportive behaviours (Lee et al., 2018).

In comparison, there is limited evidence synthesis on the process of parenting partner involvement in postpartum interventions, such as discussion or co-utilization of intervention content within dyads. Systematic reviews and meta-analyses of postpartum mental health and parenting interventions often focus on the efficacy of the included interventions, omitting information about parenting partner involvement or their participatory behaviours (Alderdice et al., 2013; C. Dennis & Dowswell, 2013; Fernandes et al., 2022; Lewkowitz et al., 2024; Mihelic et al., 2017; Min et al., 2023). Systematic reviews of partner-inclusive mental health and parenting interventions similarly focus on the efficacy of the included interventions. Description of parenting partner involvement within these reviews, if available, are limited to attendance of sessions (Alves et al., 2018; Gonzalez et al., 2023; Pilkington et al., 2015) or presence of partner-facing content/session (Alves et al., 2018; Jeong et al., 2023). Information about how and to what degree parenting partners engage with the intervention

(i.e., process) and its effects on parenting and mental health outcomes are non-existent within these reviews.

The representativeness of systematic reviews of partner-inclusive interventions is also limited as they tend to: 1) limit their scope to specific symptom domains (e.g., depression or anxiety), and 2) rely on vague or inconsistent definitions of parenting partner inclusion. For example, Noonan et al.'s (2021) systematic review was limited to interventions for perinatal depression and anxiety, and defined partner inclusivity as having “a component that included the women’s partner or family member” (page 3). Similarly, Alves et al.’s (2017) qualitative systematic review of partner-inclusive interventions was limited to postpartum depression interventions that “included both partners in the intervention session(s)” (page 3). In addition to the narrow focus on specific symptoms, “including partner” as an eligibility criterion lacks clarity as partner inclusivity varies significantly across interventions. Some programs invite partners to a single module/session (partial participation; e.g., Thomas et al., 2014), while others expect partners at every session (total participation; e.g., Bernard et al., 2011). Many interventions simply give mothers partner-specific information to be shared (e.g., Nieto et al., 2017) – an approach commonly taken by interventions not explicitly labelled as partner-inclusive (Kinser et al., 2025). Couple-based interventions targeting both parenting partners directly also exists (Ngai & Lam, 2023), further blurring the boundaries. Thus, parenting partner inclusion is a rich but highly heterogenous literature where an exploration using inclusive and broad eligibility criteria may better capture its complexities.

Searches limited to partner-inclusive interventions further fail to consider studies that have examined parenting partner involvement in interventions not exclusively labelled as “partner-inclusive”. In an online intervention targeting postpartum depression and anxiety in Chilean first-time mothers, an analysis of text messages exchanged between mothers and intervention facilitators revealed significant parenting partner involvement (Fernández et al., 2024). Specifically, mothers reported having watched intervention content videos together with their partners, even though no explicit partner-directed content or instructions to include partners were given. Similarly, the Mamma Mia program, an internet-based perinatal depression prevention strategy, found that the participating mothers shared parenting information, such as soothing the baby and breastfeeding, with their partners (Kinser et al., 2025). Reviews focusing exclusively on partner-inclusive interventions thus overlook how mothers may involve parenting partners in mental health and parenting programs independently.

In sum, existing syntheses fall short of clarifying how parenting partners are engaged, to what extent, and how their involvement influences outcomes. Systematic reviews to date are constrained by narrow symptom foci, vague or inconsistent definitions of “partner inclusion,” and a tendency to overlook informal, mother-initiated forms of parenting partner participation. A scoping review is therefore warranted to map the full breadth of postpartum mental health and parenting interventions—whether explicitly labelled as partner-inclusive or not—that report any form of parenting partner engagement. Given the heterogeneity of study designs and the conceptual immaturity of “partner inclusion” as a construct, a scoping review offers the methodological flexibility needed to capture the range and nature of parenting partner involvement and to identify key knowledge gaps that can inform future intervention design, evaluation, and policy.

Current Study

The proposed scoping review aims to address several limitations identified in existing literature on parenting partner involvement in postpartum interventions by (1) broadening the scope beyond interventions explicitly labeled as “partner-inclusive,” (2) including all types and degrees of parenting partner engagement regardless of format or delivery mode, and (3) mapping how parenting partners are involved, whether directly through program design or indirectly via maternal sharing. More specifically, this review will include psychological, psychosocial, educational, and behavioural mental health and parenting interventions delivered during the postpartum period that report any form of parenting partner engagement. Multiple databases, an inclusive search strategy, and manual forward searching of intervention articles will be used to ensure identification of all relevant studies.

Objective: The objective of this scoping review is to map the existing literature on psychological, psychosocial, and educational postpartum mental health and parenting interventions that describe any form of parenting partner involvement, in order to characterize how partners are engaged, to what extent, and in what ways their participation is reported to influence intervention processes or outcomes.

A preliminary search of MEDLINE, the Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews and *JBI Evidence Synthesis* was conducted and no current or underway systematic reviews or scoping reviews on the topic were identified.

Review question

How, and to what extent, are parenting partners involved in postpartum mental health and parenting interventions, and in what ways is that involvement reported to influence intervention processes or outcomes?

Inclusion criteria

As per the PCC framework (Participant Concept Context), we will include articles that focus on the following:

Participants

Mothers (woman-identifying primary caregiver of an infant or young child) aged 18 years or older who have given birth within the past five years and their parenting partners — spouses, co-parents, or intimate partners identified as sharing caregiving responsibilities.

Concept

Any partner involvement/engagement in a postpartum mental health or parenting intervention, including but not limited to:

- Direct attendance or co-participation (single session, multiple sessions, couple-based)
- Indirect involvement (e.g., independent sharing of materials)
- Digital, in-person, hybrid, or self-directed formats
- Individual (one-on-one), couple, or group delivery
- Outcomes or process data that attribute changes in outcome to partner involvement

No restriction on outcome type (symptom change, parenting behaviour, engagement metrics, satisfaction, etc.). Intervention may or may not be explicitly labelled “partner-inclusive”.

Context

Any intervention targeting postpartum mental health (e.g., depression, anxiety, stress) and/or parenting (e.g., bonding, breastfeeding, co-parenting skills).

- Delivered at any preventive or treatment level (primary, secondary, tertiary)
- Any setting (healthcare, community, home-based, online) and geographic location

Types of sources

We will include a broad range of study designs to comprehensively capture the extent and nature of the evidence related to partner involvement. Eligible study designs include:

- **Experimental and quasi-experimental designs**, such as randomized controlled trials (RCTs), non-randomized controlled trials, pre-post intervention studies, and interrupted time-series studies, provided that they offer information on partner engagement or maternal communication processes.
- **Analytical observational studies**, including prospective and retrospective cohort studies, case-control studies, and analytical cross-sectional studies that report on partner involvement in the context of mother-focused parenting or mental health interventions.
- **Qualitative studies**, such as those employing interviews, focus groups, or ethnographic methods, that explore mothers’ decision-making around partner involvement, communication patterns, or partner responses.
- **Mixed-methods studies**, which integrate both quantitative and qualitative data, will also be included if they report on the phenomenon of interest.

Systematic and meta-analyses will not be included; however, the reference list for relevant reviews will be searched for potential articles to include. Dissertations and theses will also be considered for inclusion in this scoping review. No restrictions will be placed on geographic or clinical (e.g., health-care, community, home-based) setting or intervention modality. Studies published in English will be included. There will be no date limit.

Methods

We will conduct the review in accordance with the JBI methodology for scoping reviews (Aromataris et al., 2024). The review will be reported following the Preferred Reporting Items for Scoping Reviews (PRISMA-ScR) guidelines.

Search strategy

The search strategy will aim to locate all relevant peer-reviewed studies and theses/dissertations on the scoping review topic. To develop a full search strategy, the text words contained in the titles and abstracts of relevant seed articles, and the index terms used to describe these seed articles will be used. The search strategy, including all identified keywords and index terms, will be adapted for each database. Reference lists for relevant reviews will be searched for potential articles to include.

Studies in English will be included. There will be no date limit. Searches will be conducted in the following databases: MEDLINE, PsycINFO, Web of Science, SocINDEX with Full Text, CINAHL Plus with Full Text, and ProQuest Dissertations & Theses.

Study/Source of evidence selection

Following the search, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into Covidence, with duplicates removed both automatically and by hand. A pilot test of study screening will be conducted to ensure agreement among reviewers. Raw percent agreement will then be calculated between the two reviewers. A minimum of 85% raw agreement must be met during the pilot test of study screening prior to proceeding with screening the rest of the retrieved records. If not met, inclusion criteria will be clarified and discordance will be discussed, then the pilot will be repeated using a new sample until the threshold is met.

Two stage screening procedure will be utilized as information about parenting partner involvement are at times unavailable in the title or the abstract, and can only be identified through full-text screening. Initial screening will involve assessment of titles and abstracts against the inclusion criteria by two or more independent reviewers. During the initial screening, studies that do not explicitly mention partner involvement in the title or in the abstract but otherwise meet the inclusion criteria will be flagged. Flagged studies will then undergo full-text keyword search to identify studies where partner involvement is reported only in the body of the article. PDFs will be searched in duplicate using the following term clusters: (i) generic partner terms, (ii) gender-specific partner terms, and (iii) inclusive/same-sex partner terms (full list in Appendix III). Pilot testing will be conducted for both stages. Records flagged by either reviewer will proceed to full eligibility assessment.

The full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by two or more independent reviewers. Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence at full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a PRISMA flow diagram.

Data extraction

A standardized data extraction form based on the recommendations put forth by Pollock *et al* (Pollock et al., 2023), published by JBI Evidence Synthesis, will be developed and used to ensure that reviewers are aligned in their data extraction (see Appendix II for example). Details specific to the research question such as type of participants, type of design, type of intervention delivered, and the outcomes related to partner involvement will be included in the data extraction chart. In addition, details about the study type (e.g., primary peer-reviewed study), design (randomized control trial), sample age and demographics, setting and location, and process and outcome data will be collected from each study. Two independent researchers will complete the data extractions using Qualtrics. Each reviewer will extract half of the identified articles. A 25% spot check will be performed where the reviewers will review 25% of each other's extractions. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer. In the case that disagreement arises in more than 30% of the articles reviewed during the spot check, rest of

the extractions will be reviewed by each reviewer to ensure alignment. The data extraction form will be iteratively and continuously updated as needed, with changes noted as protocol deviation. If appropriate, authors of papers will be contacted to request missing or additional data, where required.

Data analysis and presentation

Data from included studies will be tabulated, then summarized with simple descriptive statistics (e.g., counts and proportions) to show when, where, and how partner involvement appears across interventions. Qualitative descriptions of partner roles and engagement will be grouped into recurrent themes and categories. Outcomes linked to partner involvement will also be tabulated and described, including the types of measures used, evidence type, and the suggested association (e.g., depression scores as measured by EPDS significantly lower when partner attended at least one session). A narrative summary regarding how the results align with the objectives and research questions will be provided.

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None

Author contributions

J.W.J. conceived the study and the research question. J.W.J. developed the inclusion criteria and the search strategy, planned the data analysis, and drafted the protocol. All co-authors reviewed the initial study proposal and provided critical feedback. L.T.M. and D.E.C. offered ongoing feedback throughout the project.

Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this project.

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Appendices

Appendix I: Search strategy

MEDLINE (Ovid)

#	Query
1.	exp Postpartum Period/
2.	exp Peripartum Period/
3.	postpartum.tw,kf.
4.	postnatal.tw,kf.
5.	post-natal.tw,kf.
6.	perinatal.tw,kf.
7.	peri-natal.tw,kf.
8.	peripartum.tw,kf.
9.	peri-partum.tw,kf.
10.	"transition to parenthood".tw,kf.
11.	"transition to motherhood".tw,kf.
12.	(exp Postpartum Period/ or exp Peripartum Period/) and exp Mothers/
13.	(exp Postpartum Period/ or exp Peripartum Period/) and exp Parents/
14.	((postpartum or postnatal or post-natal or perinatal or peri-natal or peripartum or peri-partum or "transition to parenthood" or "transition to motherhood") adj3 (maternal or mother or mothers or parent or parents or couple or couples)).tw,kf.
15	1 or 2 or 3 or 4 or 5 or 6 or 7 or 8 or 9 or 10 or 11 or 12 or 13 or 14
16.	exp Depression/ or exp Depressive Disorder/
17.	exp Anxiety/ or exp Anxiety Disorders/ or exp Generalized Anxiety Disorder/
18.	exp Stress, Psychological/
19.	exp Stress Disorders, Post-Traumatic/
20.	exp Emotions/
21.	exp Psychological Distress/
22.	exp Mental Health/
23.	exp Depression, Postpartum/
24.	exp Parenting/
25.	exp Parent-Child Relations/
26.	exp Mother-Child Relations/
27.	((postpartum or postnatal or post-natal or perinatal or peri-natal or peripartum or peri-partum or "transition to parenthood" or "transition to motherhood") adj3 (depress* or depression or "depressive disorder" or anxi* or anxiety or "anxiety disorder" or stress or emotion* or distress or "psychological distress" or anger or "mental health*" or "low mood" or mood* or trauma* or PTSD or "post-traumatic" or psycho* or affect* or parenting or "parent-child relations" or "parent-child interaction*" or "mother-child relations" or "mother-child interaction*" or "mother-infant relations" or "mother-infant interaction*" or "infant care" or bond* or "parent-infant bonding" or "mother-infant bonding" or crying or feed* or sleep* or co-regulat* or "parenting stress" or "parenting self-efficacy" or "parenting efficacy" or "parenting confidence" or nurtur* or "parental behavi*" or "responsiveness" or attachment* or "parental engagement" or "parenting behavior" or "parenting behaviour" or "parental sensitivity" or "emotional availability" or scaffolding or "developmental support" or "maternal sensitivity" or "behavioral engagement" or "discipline practices" or "parenting practices")).tw,kf.
28.	16 or 17 or 18 or 19 or 20 or 21 or 22 or 23 or 24 or 25 or 26 or 27

29.	intervention*.ti.
30.	program.ti.
31.	trial*.ti.
32.	treat*.ti.
33.	therap*.ti.
34.	counsel*.ti.
35.	tool*.ti.
36.	education*.ti.
37.	prevent*.ti.
38.	training.ti.
39.	mentor*.ti.
40.	coach*.ti.
41.	resource.ti.
42.	29 or 30 or 31 or 32 or 33 or 34 or 35 or 36 or 37 or 38 or 39 or 40 or 41
43.	15 and 28 and 42

Appendix II: Data extraction instrument

Field	Brief description/extraction rules	Example entry (mock data)
Citation	Author(s), year	Smith 2024
Country & setting	Nation + care setting (e.g., Canada; community health centre)	UK; online platform
Evidence-source type	Primary study, mixed-methods, dissertation, etc.	Primary peer-reviewed study
Study design	RCT, quasi-exp, qualitative, mixed	Cluster RCT
Population details	Postpartum ≤ 5 y; age ≥ 18 ; parity, risk status	Primiparous; mean age 29, at-risk of depression (EPDS ≥ 10)
Partner characteristics	Relationship & gender (if stated)	Male spouse
Intervention aim	Mental-health, parenting, both	Parenting + PPD prevention
Intervention delivery	Format (group/individual), mode (in-person, app), level (primary/secondary/tertiary prevention)	Group; hybrid; secondary
Partner-involvement type	Use predefined codes (direct-full, direct-partial, parallel stream, mother-mediated, other)	Direct-partial
Degree / intensity	# partner sessions or % partner-focused content	2 of 8 sessions
Definition of partner inclusion	Author's verbatim wording	"Partner attendance in two workshops"
Outcomes linked to partners	Any outcome attributed to partner involvement (symptoms, breastfeeding, engagement)	EPDS \downarrow greater when partner attended
Process data	Engagement, fidelity, acceptability measures tied to partners	85 % partner attendance

Key findings / conclusions	1–2 lines on partner influence	Partners boosted coping self-efficacy
Knowledge gaps noted	Gaps authors highlight re: partners	Need measures of partner burden
Reviewer notes	Free text for uncertainties or contacting authors	Sample size unclear

Appendix III: Full-text search terms for screening

	Keyword search terms
Generic partner terms	“partner”, “intimate partner”, “significant other”, “spouse”, “co-parent”, “coparent”, “co parent”
Gender-specific terms	“father”, “dad”, “paternal”, “husband”, “male partner”, “boyfriend”, “fiancé”
Same-sex & inclusive terms	wife (when the postpartum parent is female), female partner, girlfriend, “same-sex partner”, queer partner